

просто экономический проект – неоспоримо и его социально-экономическое значение.

Сегодня в Карабахе создается серьезная транспортная и энергетическая инфраструктура для создания самовоспроизводящейся экосистемы. Освобожденные территории обладают для этого значительными экономическими ресурсами. Здесь уже с чистого листа создаются самые благоприятные условия формирования экономики XXI века.

Реализация проекта будет осуществляться по пяти ключевым компонентам:

- жилищный сектор;
- производство;
- социальные услуги;
- «умное сельское хозяйство»;
- альтернативная энергетика.

На территории сел Агалы 1, Агалы 2 и Агалы 3 Зангиланского района идет строительство 200 домов с использованием инновационных стройматериалов. Предполагается, что дома будут автономными, то есть, будут обеспечивать свою потребность в электроэнергии за счет возобновляемых источников. Инженерные коммуникации, системы отопления в домах также будут созданы на основе «умных» технологий.

В этих селах планируется построить современные школы, детские сады, поликлиники и центры электронного управления, сформировать инфраструктуру туризма. Все жилые дома, социальные объекты, административные здания, объекты общепита, процессы переработки и производства сельскохозяйственной продукции будут обеспечиваться альтернативными источниками энергии.

Проект также предусматривает наличие на территории экологических систем отопления, «умных» систем ликвидации отходов и освещения, современного способа градостроительства и инфраструктуры, наличие велодорожек и станций для подзарядки электромобилей, экологические сенсоры контроля и камеры безопасности, а также возможности дистанционных медицинских консультаций и рекреативные зоны.

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DEHYDRATION OF DIESEL FUEL WITH HYDROGELS

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Abstract

This article considers the prospect of using "smart" materials, i.e. hydrogels in diesel fuel to reduce corrosion. Theoretical foundations are given, as well as laboratory tests on the dehydration of diesel fuel.

Keywords: diesel fuel, corrosion, hydrogels, dehydration, materials science, oil products.

The reduction of metal corrosion in oil products is important in ensuring the operational reliability of transport equipment. Corrosive wear of mechanism parts is due to the presence of moisture, sulfur compounds, oxidized hydrocarbons, etc. in oil products. Corrosion is exposed not only to metal parts in oil products, but also to the metal surfaces of the body due to the influence of the external environment [1,2].

Corrosion of metals in petroleum products has its own specific features and largely determined by the presence of dissolved as well as free water in them. In real conditions of storage, transportation and use of petroleum products, they are constantly saturated with water and condensed on metal surfaces. The water content in fuels can vary widely [from 0.001 to 0.01% (wt.)] and depends on the operating conditions of the equipment and on climatic factors [3]. The main source of water accumulation in oil products is atmospheric moisture, which, when the temperature of oil products and the walls of reservoirs (fuel tanks, etc.) changes, condenses on metal surfaces [4].

Condensation of water vapor occurs, as a rule, in the volume of oil products, and then water drops penetrate through the thickness or film of oil products to the metal surface. At the same time, water drops dissolve in themselves and carry away water-soluble products of oxidation of hydrocarbon and non-hydrocarbon components of oil products. In addition, water, due to its high polarity, can attract polar low-stable compounds that do not dissolve in water and transport them to metal surfaces. Thus, a water film is almost always formed between the metal and the oil product, which contributes to the development of electrochemical corrosion processes.

Thus, the corrosion of metals in oil product + water + metal systems is complex and is determined by the development of both chemical and (mainly) electrochemical processes. Corrosion products are formed, as a rule, outside the corroding metal surface. They consist mainly of compounds of a crystalline structure with a particle size of up to 5 - 10 microns and represent a great danger for precision pairs with small gaps.

To protect parts of machines and mechanisms from the effects associated with the external environment, special protective and anti-corrosion additives are added to lubricating oils, which provide not only high-performance properties of oils under normal conditions, but also prevent the undesirable action of water, chlorine compounds, acids, hydrogen sulfide and other corrosive substances on the metal during periods of conservation, interruptions in work.

The protective properties of petroleum products can only be improved with the help of additives. The

essence of the action of corrosion inhibitors lies in their increased wetting ability of petroleum products with respect to metals in the oil product + water system, to inhibition of the anodic, cathodic (or simultaneously cathodic and anodic) processes of electrochemical corrosion and to the formation of strong adsorption-chemisorption protective films.

At the same time, along with the use of anti-corrosion additives to protect metal surfaces from corrosion, it is important that there is no moisture in oil products, which can be achieved by the action of hydrophilic gels (hydrogels).

Gels are complex chemical compositions capable of absorbing moisture from petroleum products (gasolines, diesel fuels, lubricants).

At the Department of "Transport Power Plants" of the Tashkent State Transport University, together with LLC TNII "Chemical Technology", experiments were carried out on the absorption of moisture from gasoline, diesel fuels and oils (Fig. 1).

Circles indicate covalent crosslinks between polymer chains.

Pic. 1 - Schematic representation of a polymer gel

It was found that the gel absorbs water 80-100 times its mass, depending on the temperature, concentration and structure of the gel, while the structure of hydrogels is not destroyed, because. consists of polymer chains having parallel and cross links.

In 3 cones with a capacity of 150 ml, place - in the first 5 g, in the second 10 g, in the third 15 g of hydrogel. Then pour 100 ml into each flask. diesel fuel [5].

1 - part of the experiments.

Pour pure diesel fuel and 5 g of hydrogel into the control flask, add 10 ml each into the remaining flasks. water. Experiments are carried out at room temperature and observe the time during which all the water is absorbed in the cones.

Table 1

Effect of Hydrogel Concentration on Water Absorption Rate

Test time, sec (min.)	5 y.	10 y.	15y.
Experiences			
1	65 sec		
2		25 sec	
3			18 cec

2 - part of the experiments.

Prepare similar samples of diesel fuel with water and hydrogels. To determine the effect of temperature on the rate of moisture absorption in diesel fuel, to do

this, prepare a water bath and heat to a temperature of 50°C, 70°C and 80°C, and each time observe the absorption of moisture, and determine the time for complete absorption of moisture in each sample.

Table 2**The influence of temperature on the rate of water absorption**

Test time, sec (min)	50°C	70°C	80°C
Hydrogel concentration y.			
5 g hydrogels	52 sec	39 sec	35 sec
10 g hydrogels	20 sec	17 sec	15 sec
15 g hydrogels	12 sec	10 sec	8 sec

Observations showed that within 10 min. the gel completely absorbed the water.

At the same time, the highest efficiency of the process was noted at a gel concentration of 10 g. and temperature 40-500 C.

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CORROSION PROTECTION OF HEAT EXCHANGERS USED ON THE DEVICE FOR AMINE CLEANING OF REGENERATION GASES "SHURTAN OIL AND GAS PRODUCTION DEPARTMENT"

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ЗАЩИТА ТЕПЛООБМЕННОГО АППАРАТА ОТ КОРРОЗИИ, ПРИМЕНЯЕМОГО В УСТРОЙСТВЕ ПО ОЧИСТКЕ РЕГЕНЕРАЦИОННЫХ ГАЗОВ С ПОМОЩЬЮ АМИНА «ШУРТАНСКОЕ НЕФТЕГАЗОДОБЫВАЮЩЕЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ»

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Abstract

One of the most pressing problems of gas-processing enterprises is the large corrosion of the corpus callosum of the horizontal heat exchanger, which is used in the process of regeneration of the absorbed absorbent (diethanolamine) in the absorption of gas. This article discusses the causes of corrosion on the body of the appliance and how to deal with them.

Аннотация

Одной из актуальных проблем на газоперерабатывающих предприятиях является быстрая коррозия корпуса горизонтального кожухотрубчатого теплообменника, применяемой в процессе регенерации насыщенного абсорбента (диэтанолamina) при абсорбционной очистке природного газа от кислых компонентов. В данной статье рассмотрены причины коррозии корпуса устройства и способы ее устранения.

Keywords: casing tubular heat exchanger, absorbent, diethanolamine, tubular bead, intercellular space.